

Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds. Part-VII* : Spasmolytic Activities of Isothiazole Carboxylic Esters

S. K. NAIK, S. S. MEHER and A. NAYAK

Biochemistry Laboratory, Sambalpur University, Sambalpur-768 017

Manuscript received 5 October 1982, accepted 19 July 1983

Several isothiazole esters have been synthesised with a view to evaluate their spasmolytic activities against acetylcholine, histamine and barium chloride as spasmogen. The antagonism studies indicate that these compounds are nonspecific in their actions. The ED_{50} values of the compounds have been evaluated against diphenhydramine as standard.

WE had earlier reported¹ the anticholinergic activities of several thiazole carboxylic esters on guineapig ileum using atropine and trantergan as standards. The spasmolytic activities of several aromatic² and heterocyclic³ esters have also been reported. Considering the therapeutic importance of isothiazole compounds⁴ several esters possessing isothiazole moiety have been synthesised and screened on smooth muscles using acetylcholine, histamine and barium chloride as stimulants.

The basic esters in the form of their hydrochlorides were obtained by condensing the isothiazole carboxyl chloride with dialkylamino ethanol. 3-Phenylisothiazole-4-carboxylic acid and 3-*p*-chlorophenylisothiazole-4-carboxylic acids used in the synthesis of esters were obtained by the hydrolysis of the respective cyano derivatives using H_2SO_4 (Scheme 1).

- 1a R = Phenyl, X = $-N(CH_3)_2$
 1b R = Phenyl, X = $-N(C_2H_5)_2$
 1c R = Phenyl, X = $-N$ (cyclopropyl)
 1d R = Phenyl, X = $-N$ (cyclohexyl)
 1e R = *p*-Chlorophenyl, X = $-N(CH_3)_2$
 1f R = *p*-Chlorophenyl, X = $-N(C_2H_5)_2$
 1g R = *p*-Chlorophenyl, X = $-N$ (cyclopropyl)
 1h R = *p*-Chlorophenyl, X = $-N$ (cyclohexyl)

Scheme 1

Spasmolytic tests :

The anticholinergic and antihistaminic activities of the compounds were evaluated on isolated strips

of guineapig ileum by cumulative method using acetylcholine, histamine acid phosphate and barium chloride as the spasmogens. Since the ileum possesses several receptors for cholinergic activities, the histamine receptors were blocked by the addition of $10^{-6}M$ solution of mepyrimine maleate and for antihistamine activities the cholinergic receptors were blocked by adding atrophine hydrochloride ($10^{-6}M$) solution to the test bath. The temperature of the bath was maintained at 37° and oxygenation was effected by passing compressed air to the bath from a calibrated tuberculin syringe. Spasmogens in varying concentration in the perfusing fluid were used as the agonists for inducing contraction. The contraction of the ileum was recorded on the smoked drums using various esters as the antagonists by cumulative method. Different ileum preparations were used for the antagonism study. The ED_{50} values of the compounds were also determined by curative⁶ method in the same test system.

Results and Discussion

The cholinergic antagonism study of (4-dimethylaminoethyl)-3-phenylisothiazole carboxylate (1a) at $1.4 \times 10^{-6}M$ showed shifting of the LDR curve towards right indicating the nature of antagonism to be either competitive or non-competitive acting at different sites of the receptors. But by decreasing the concentration of the drug it produced concentration dependent unsurmountable depression of the response. Similar were the observations in case of other esters indicating the non-competitive antagonism where the drugs reduce the stimulus of the agonist by interacting with receptors which differ from those of the agonist and which are located anywhere on the chain of events leading from receptor occupation of the agonist to the effect. Similar effect was observed in the case of histaminic antagonism studies. The non-specific antagonism of the compounds may be due to the placement of adjacent large atoms such as nitrogen and sulphur. This situation did not exist in the case of analogous

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND SPASMOLYTIC TESTS FOR THE ESTERS

Structure	m.p.**	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Anticholinergic		Antihistaminic		Antibarium	
		Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	ED ₅₀ mg	Potency*	ED ₅₀ mg	Potency*	ED ₅₀ mg	Potency*
1a		48.06 (48.13)	5.18 (5.15)	5.17 (8.02)	0.03	0.7	0.20	0.25	0.50	0.6
1b	178 (d)	45.50 (45.62)	5.71 (5.83)	7.39 (7.42)	0.08	0.5	0.60	0.25	0.75	0.8
1c	194 (d)	45.70 (45.86)	5.24 (5.33)	7.36 (7.46)	0.20	0.1	0.80	0.03	0.60	0.8
1d	203 (d)	47.15 (47.30)	5.60 (5.65)	7.15 (7.19)	0.50	0.06	0.90	0.05	0.80	0.8
1e	182 (d)	39.12 (39.25)	4.10 (3.97)	6.42 (6.54)	0.60	0.1	0.70	0.03	0.60	0.5
1f	196 (d)	37.50 (37.71)	4.51 (4.60)	4.06 (6.14)	0.60	0.05	0.90	0.25	0.70	0.6
1g	210 (d)	37.70 (37.88)	4.20 (4.18)	6.25 (6.16)	0.80	0.15	0.90	0.06	0.70	0.6
1h	242 (d)	39.26 (39.31)	4.63 (4.48)	6.13 (5.98)	0.80	0.25	0.90	0.08	0.80	0.8

* Relative to diphenhydramine.

** Numbers indicate decomposition temperature.

TABLE 2—CUMULATIVE DOSE-RESPONSE RECORDINGS FOR ANTAGONISM STUDY OF COMPOUND 1a

Amount of acetylcholine in the bath μg	Conc. × 10 M	log (conc.)	Response (mm)	Response in the presence of antagonist		
				3.6 × 10 ⁻⁶ M	7.2 × 10 ⁻⁶ M	9.8 × 10 ⁻⁶ M
50	0.0275	-7.506	0	0	0	0
100	0.0550	-7.2596	3	0	0	0
200	0.1101	-6.9582	18	7	0	0
300	0.1652	-6.7819	49	23	5	0
400	0.2203	-6.0569	84	45	15	0
500	0.2754	-6.5607	92	57	22	4
600	0.3305	-6.4808	97	61	24	5
700	0.3856	-6.4138	97	61	24	5
800	0.4407	-6.3558	97	61	24	5
900	0.4958	-6.3046	97	61	24	5

thiazole compounds where the antagonism was found to be specific as reported earlier¹. The ED₅₀ values of the compounds using diphenhydramine as standard were evaluated by curative method using acetylcholine, histamine or barium chloride as spasmogen. The relative potency of these drugs were measured with respect to the standard which indicated that none of these compounds have significant activities.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrect. 3-Phenyl isothiazole-4-carboxylic acid and 3-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-isothiazole-4-carboxylic acid of m.p. 143 and 162°, respectively were prepared from their corresponding cyano derivatives by hydrolysis² with conc. sulphuric acid.

3-Phenylisothiazole-4-carbonyl chloride: A mixture of 3-phenylisothiazole-4-carboxylic acid (2.05 g; 10 m mole) and thionyl chloride (5 ml) was warmed on a water bath at 70 to 75° for 30 min. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure to afford a thick oil which was used directly.

β-Dimethylaminoethyl-3-phenylisothiazole carboxylate dihydrochloride (1a): A solution of 3-phenylisothiazole-4-carbonyl chloride (2.25 g; 10 m mole) and β-dimethylamino ethanol (1.1 g; 12 m mole) in

toluene (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. After cooling the hydrochloride of the dimethylamino ethanol precipitated out and was filtered. The toluene solution was dried using anhydrous CaCl₂. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with dry ether and dry HCl gas passed through the solution which precipitated the hydrochloride as white solid. It was filtered, washed with ether and finally crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. (196°, d), yield 45%. (Found: C, 48.10; H, 5.21; N, 8.12. C₁₄H₁₈N₂SO₂Cl₂ requires C, 48.13; H, 5.16; N, 8.02%). The analytical and spasmolytic test results of various esters obtained from the two acid chlorides are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

References

- R. K. BEHERA, P. N. DHAL and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1981, 18, 229.
- E. C. MCMANUS, J. M. BOCHAY and K. H. BEYER, *J. Pharm. Expt. Therap.*, 1953, 93, 364.
- (a) S. WIELDING, *Acta Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 1957, 13, 59.
(b) R. DAHLEBOM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1953, 7, 879.
- (a) R. SLACK and K. R. H. WOOLDRIDGE, *Adv. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1965, 4, 104.
(b) M. DAVIS, *Adv. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1972, 14, 43.
- (a) J. GOERDELER and W. METTLET, *Ber.*, 1963, 96, 944.
(b) M. S. C. GRANT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3842.
(c) M. P. L. CATON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 446.
- S. WIELDING, *Acta Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 1952, 8, 177.